

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Prasetyanti****FIRST NAME: Anastasia****PROGRAM CODE: MBAIO****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2019 on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. What details that books citation must have?

- Author's full name, book title, year of publication, place of publication, and page number you have taken information from.
- Author's surname and first name, year of publication, book title, book edition, place of publication, publisher, and page number you have taken information from.¹**
- Author's surname and first name, book title, book edition, year of edition, publisher, and page number you have taken information from.
- Initial of author's first name, book title, publishing date of the book, edition, publisher, city of publication, and page number you have taken information from.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack. Period 4* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 57.

2. **What is one of the essential steps in writing where it involves selecting and developing a subject for writing, including brainstorming and collecting some information beforehand?**

Prewriting²

Clustering

Analyzing

Listing

3. **Which of the following are the three kind of questions that researchers ask according to Turabian?**

Logical, practical, and hypocrite questions.

Simple, conceptual, and related questions.

Related, practical, and updated questions.

Conceptual, practical, and applied questions.³

4. **How should a researcher record his sources?**

Shortened, clear, and tidy.

Fully, accurately, and appropriately.⁴

Carefully, put them into writing, and fully.

Correctly, precisely, carefully.

² Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000* (Massachusetts, United States of America: Great Source Education Group, 1999), 45.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* (Chicago, United States of America: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 16.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, 25.

5. **As a writer, it is important to think about our reader and to understand them better as we work through our project. To start with, what sort of questions we ask ourselves in order to know our reader well?**

- What kind of issue will interest them, who will read my report, when will I present my report to them, why would they need to know about the answer/claim, and how will I represent the claim.
- Where the research takes place and where do my readers live, why do they need the answer/claim, will they argue the claim.
- Who will read my report, what do they expect me to do, how much can I expect them to know already, and how will readers respond to the solution/answer in my main claim.⁵**
- Who are my audience, what will make them listen to my argument, what resource should I use so it will appear familiar to them.

6. **What options that a writer can do to support his writing ideas?**

- Researching, interviewing, or finding sources.
- Explain, define, describe, argue, illustrate, reflect, analyze, or compare.⁶**
- Analyze, think, search the internet, compare few research results, or answer few reader's questions.
- Compare, research, interview, record, or define.

7. **What are the two fundamentally kinds of argument that we must distinguish because readers evaluate them differently?**

⁵ Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams, *The Craft of Research*, (Chicago, United States of America: The University of Chicago Press, 2008), 26-27.

⁶ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, 64.

One kind of argument backs up a claim with reasons based on evidence and the other infers a claim from a reason and warrant.⁷

One kind of argument backs up a claim with data and the other backs up a claim with reasons.

One kind of argument backs up a claim with evidence and the other with possible answer from the writer.

One kind of argument backs up a claim with facts and the other with research result.

8. **In many fields, report begins with abstract, a paragraph that tells readers what they will find in the report. What should a writer do on their abstract?**

Write why he talks about the problem, a short sentence about the theme, and the explanation.

A thank you note or acknowledgement, background of the problem, and the main point of the research.

State the min point of the research and a glimpse of the conclusion.

State the research problem, announce key theme, state the main point or launching point that anticipates the main point.⁸

9. **What is the importance of citing sources?**

So readers can find the sources easily.

To avoid plagiarism, for readers to trust your evidence, and to honor your sources.⁹

To be a credible writer.

⁷ Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams, 169.

⁸ Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams, 211.

⁹ Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams, 195-196.

To guide the reader of where did you get your source from.

10. **What are the three level of detail on writing?**

Make an opening of the topic, create an argument of your topic, completing sentences of the argument and add more details.

Opening, main point, closing.

Controlling (topic) sentences name and control the topic, clarifying sentences support the main point and help make the topic clearer, completing sentences and add specific details to complete the point.¹⁰

Explaining the main topic to reader, going deeper with explanation, and citing the resource at the end.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020.

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¹⁰ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, 64.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.